

Conflicts and conflict management styles of student nurses in a revived face-to-face learning modality

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ABSTRACT

Conflict is a fundamental part of life, emerging in many different contexts. As tertiary institutions resumed in-person classes following the pandemic's shift to online learning, student nurses like other students encountered numerous challenges and had to make essential adjustments. This quantitative-descriptive study aimed to identify the conflicts encountered by student nurses as they transitioned from online to face-to-face learning and describe the conflict management styles they employ in response. A total of 144 respondents answered a researcher-made survey questionnaire to collect necessary data, which were then analyzed using frequency count, percentage distribution, weighted mean score, and standard deviation. Findings indicated that mostly experienced conflicts were intrapersonal; moreover, collaborative and compromising styles were prominent as their conflict management styles. It can be concluded that the respondents mainly involve internal struggles as their conflicts during the transition between learning modalities, highlighting the need for interventions and training programs, which could also enhance their application of other conflict management styles. Additionally, empirical recommendations are provided for educational institutions, relevant stakeholders, and future researchers to enhance the student body's general well-being and academic success concerning understanding and managing conflicts.

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INTRODUCTION

Conflict arises in various settings worldwide. Its nature is often linked to disagreement, contradiction, or incompatibility (Rahim, 2023; Wallensteen, 2015). In other words, conflict refers to any scenario where incompatible goals, cognitions, or emotions exist within or between individuals or groups, leading to opposition or antagonistic interactions. Though a conflict is not necessarily a negative feature as it often leads to constructive problem-solving, it still affects people in the form of experienced challenges, inevitable adjustments, and life transitions (Dansereau, 2022; Trueba et al., 2014).

As such, it could be argued that the most recent global health catastrophe (COVID-19 pandemic) had also caused conflicts (Adisa et al., 2021). Global reports have shown that the pandemic disrupted all aspects of life, resulting in challenges, adjustments, transitions, and conflicts. Furthermore, it has also given birth to numerous drastic effects on education globally. In fact, many scholars have conveyed that such a pandemic scenario represented not merely a shift from formal to informal learning, but rather an educational crisis (Adnan & Anwar, 2020; Bjursell, 2020; Obiakor & Adeniran, 2020; Ria, 2021).

In higher education, the pandemic created unprecedented challenges for policymakers and educational institutions globally. They had to address issues such as mitigating learning losses, implementing remote learning, safely reopening schools, and ensuring that underrepresented, vulnerable, and disadvantaged students were not left behind (Dubey & Pandey, 2020; Verde & Valero, 2021). This abrupt shift away from traditional classrooms forced schools and universities to quickly adopt virtual and digital strategies worldwide. These transitions were the shifts from traditional face-to-face classes to hybrid or totally online classes while trying to help students, lecturers, professors, and personnel.

Consequently, students and teachers encountered conflicts manifesting as difficulties and adjustments during the transition to online classrooms. Additionally, they grappled with emotional vulnerabilities, as indicated by Kalloo et al.'s (2020) study conducted in Trinidad and Tobago and Wut and Xu's (2021) study in Hong Kong. These reports shed light on the multifaceted nature of the challenges faced by individuals involved in the educational process.

Meanwhile, in the Philippines, various forms of challenging circumstances have significantly impacted the ability to conduct face-to-face classes for students. This impact extended to fields such as medicine and allied health courses (e.g., nursing), which require direct interaction between instructors and students to ensure the precise application of scientific concepts and theories. As a result, these courses also faced substantial challenges and setbacks (Mondragon et al., 2022; Obon & Balila, 2022). In particular, for student nurses, the pandemic disrupted traditional face-to-face learning modalities and presented a host of challenges. Foremost among these challenges was the limited access to clinical placements, depriving students of essential hands-on experiences vital for developing critical skills in patient care. The transition to online learning compounded these difficulties, with virtual platforms struggling to replicate the interactive and practical aspects of nursing education (Mondragon et al., 2022; Obon & Balila, 2022). Moreover, interpersonal conflicts within academic communities also emerged, stemming from the disruption of social connections and peer support networks in the virtual learning environment (Purwanto, 2020; Tsiakara & Digelidis, 2021).

However, following over two years of sporadic distance learning due to the pandemic, the Philippine government, specifically the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), officially authorized the resumption of face-to-face classes in tertiary schools. Anchored on the assertion of Yuana et al. (2020) that transitions are processes of major change and often come with conflict, this new pedagogical transition could be argued to produce conflicts and adjustments for students, and their significance should be noticed. Student nurses, in particular, have been observed to encounter conflicts and adjustments as they navigate the complexities of this retransition. Concerns about safety protocols, adjustments to in-person interactions, and reintegration into clinical settings are among the potential sources of conflict that student nurses may face during this period. Additionally, disparities in access to resources and support systems may exacerbate existing challenges, further contributing to interpersonal tensions and conflicts

within academic communities. Thus, effective conflict management strategies, open communication channels, and supportive interventions are essential for addressing these challenges and promoting a smooth transition to face-to-face classes for student nurses in the Philippines. Consequently, this sparked the researchers' interest and motivated them to study this phenomenon, recognizing the potential impact and importance of examining these new conflicts and dynamics that have likely arisen during this transition.

While there are multiple studies (e.g., Adnan & Anwar, 2020; Bjursell, 2020; Dubey & Pandey, 2020; Milan & Lemana, 2023; Obiakor & Adeniran, 2020, among others) conducted and published about conflicts in the forms of challenges and adjustments encountered by students while they transitioned from face-to-face classes to online classes during the pandemic, there is a noticeable lacuna in the research literature concerning studies on conflicts encountered by students as the classes reverted from online classes to face-to-face settings. Additionally, there needs to be more exploration into how students (e.g., student nurses) manage their conflicts. As Rosen et al. (2018) opine, nursing students must develop proficiency in facing and resolving conflicts for success in their future high-pressure healthcare workplaces. Thus, a study concerning this group of individuals is deemed worthy of urgent research attention.

Hence, addressing the knowledge and population research gaps as described in the previous paragraph, the researchers conducted this quantitative-descriptive study that was aimed at (1) identifying the types of conflicts that are experienced by university nursing students who have undergone the reversion from online to onsite learning modality and (2) describing the styles that they employ to manage those conflicts.

Studying conflicts among student nurses during the retransition to face-to-face classes in the Philippines is imperative for understanding and addressing the multifaceted challenges they face. Firstly, conflicts can significantly impact the mental health and academic performance of student nurses, necessitating targeted interventions to support their well-being and resilience. Secondly, conflicts within academic communities can impede effective learning and collaboration, highlighting the need for conflict resolution strategies to promote a positive and inclusive learning environment. Moreover, conflicts may reveal underlying disparities in access to resources and opportunities for professional development, informing policy decisions aimed at promoting equity within nursing education and practice. Additionally, investigating conflicts can provide insights into the impact of pedagogical transitions on learning outcomes and clinical preparedness, guiding educators in adapting teaching methodologies and support services to better meet students' needs. In summary, studying conflicts among student nurses is crucial for fostering a supportive learning environment, addressing systemic inequities, and improving educational outcomes in nursing education.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the types of conflicts experienced by university nursing students who have undergone the reversion from online to onsite learning modality?
2. What conflict management styles do they employ to address those conflicts?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Revived Face-to-face Learning Modality

The COVID-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted the global education sector, leading to extensive school closures and necessitating a comprehensive shift to remote learning frameworks (Adnan & Anwar, 2020; Bjursell, 2020; Garcia-Morales et al., 2021; Obiakor & Adeniran, 2020; Ria, 2021). As cited in the study by Tadesse and Muluye (2020), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) has reported that over 180 countries had implemented nationwide closures in 2020, affecting approximately 1.5 billion students. This disruption in regular schooling has had significant consequences for students, teachers, and educational systems.

The transition to remote learning became imperative during the pandemic. Educational institutions rapidly integrated online platforms, video conferencing tools, and various digital resources to facilitate the delivery of lessons

and conduct virtual classes. Nonetheless, this shift presented several challenges. The digital divide became pronounced as students from low-income households or remote areas encountered significant barriers to accessing essential technology and reliable internet connectivity, as shown in the study of Azubuike et al. (2021) on the digital divide pertaining to access to remote learning for children in Nigeria amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. The results suggest a correlation between socioeconomic status and the digital divide, wherein students hailing from lower socioeconomic strata encounter more formidable obstacles in their efforts to avail themselves of remote learning resources. Evident variations in the availability of remote learning opportunities were noted, encompassing inequalities between pupils enrolled in public and private educational institutions. The study revealed a correlation between the educational attainment of parents and their capacity to facilitate their children's distance education. The aforementioned discoveries underscore the necessity of tackling the digital divide in order to guarantee equal educational prospects for every student in Nigeria. Similar and related results have been put forward by other studies (see Correia, 2020; Saha et al., 2021; van de Werfhorst et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the pandemic's impact on teacher and student well-being cannot be overlooked. Teachers faced the daunting task of adapting their teaching methods to the online environment, often while managing their own personal challenges. A study conducted in California, USA, and published in the Learning Policy Institute found that teachers experienced increased workload, heightened anxiety, and decreased job satisfaction during the transition to remote teaching (Carver-Thomas et al., 2021). Students, on the other hand, experienced social isolation, disrupted routines, and mental health concerns due to the lack of in-person interactions and support systems (Gopal et al., 2021; Irawan et al., 2020).

The pandemic also disrupted exams and assessments. Many standardized exams, board exams, and assessments had to be postponed, canceled, or modified, creating uncertainty among students regarding their academic progress and future prospects (Tarkar, 2020). Higher education institutions faced their own set of challenges. According to a report, international student enrollments declined due to travel restrictions and concerns about studying abroad during the pandemic (Thatcher et al., 2020). Universities and colleges also had to adapt to remote teaching and learning, impacting research activities and financial stability.

In the context of the Philippines, schools have been reopened after more than two years – one of the longest pandemic-induced school closures in the world (Maliao et al., 2023). The Philippine government made the decision to reopen schools for face-to-face classes, driven by a recognition of the challenges and conflicts posed by prolonged school closures. Remote learning, although implemented as an alternative, presented challenges in terms of accessibility, effectiveness, and quality, particularly for students from disadvantaged backgrounds (Rotas & Cahapay, 2020). Therefore, the decision to reopen schools was regarded as a strategy to enhance the educational experience by providing direct mentorship, individualized support, and immediate feedback from educators, which could significantly improve student academic outcomes. As Oducado's (2020) study conveys, the face-to-face learning modality provides opportunities for hands-on activities, practical demonstrations, and collaborative learning experiences that are often difficult to replicate in online settings. In the same way, face-to-face classes also enable educators to provide immediate feedback and personalized support, addressing the individual needs of students more effectively.

Additionally, physical classrooms are deemed to be effective in facilitating social development among students where they could experience peer interactions, socialization, and the development of important life skills. The closure of schools deprived students of these valuable opportunities for social growth and engagement. Nuñez et al. (2022) and Tagare (2023) therefore argue that reopening schools would enable students to reconnect with their peers, foster relationships, and develop social skills crucial for their overall development.

The benefits of school reopening have been seen as much more important for students in allied health programs, as for them, a face-to-face classroom provides the necessary hands-on learning and practical experience crucial for their education and future careers. Regmi and Jones (2020) assert that in-person instruction allows these students to access specialized facilities, laboratories, and clinical placements, enabling them to develop clinical skills,

proficiency in using medical equipment, and an understanding of patient care protocols, which can foster competence and confidence, preparing students for real-world healthcare settings.

While the decision to reopen schools in the Philippines was driven by educational and social considerations, the government also recognized the need to implement strict health and safety protocols (Bongolan et al., 2022). The government had to devise guidelines and protocols to minimize the risk of virus transmission among students, teachers, and staff. This included measures such as mandatory mask-wearing, physical distancing, frequent hand hygiene, regular disinfection of facilities, and temperature checks. Consequently, the decision to reopen schools during the COVID-19 pandemic was accompanied by varying perspectives among stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and health experts. Romero (2022) outlined the contrasting viewpoints, with some prioritizing the health and safety of students and communities, advocating for a cautious approach, while others emphasized the importance of reopening schools promptly to address the long-term impact on students' education and well-being. With that, it is crucial to acknowledge that the decision to reopen schools was not devoid of challenges and conflicts.

Conflicts

Conflict is an inherent aspect of human behavior that manifests in various contexts and can occur between individuals, groups, organizations, or nations. It stems from negative emotions such as anxiety, hostility, sadness, and resistance, as well as hostile responses like rivalry (Rahim, 2023; Wallensteen, 2015). In other words, conflict arises when individuals or groups perceive their interests as being hindered or adversely affected by others, leading to disagreements and inconsistencies in interpersonal and intrapersonal interactions.

Further, conflicts can be understood as a deliberate effort to hinder the achievement of goals and can emerge due to a multitude of reasons. They may arise between two or more individuals or within a group, encompassing disparities in beliefs, attitudes, comprehension, interests, needs, and even perceptions (Trueba et al., 2014). It is important to note that conflict is regarded as both a negative situation and a dynamic process. When conflicts escalate, they can give rise to intense debates, physical confrontations, and a clear disruption of peace and harmony (Barash & Webel, 2021). Such conflicts can have significant ramifications, leading to strained relationships, damaged trust, and hindered progress. However, conflicts, despite their negative connotations, possess the potential to stimulate growth and catalyze positive change within individuals and groups (Lederach, 2015). This means that when conflicts arise, they often bring underlying tensions and divergent viewpoints to the surface, providing an opportunity for open dialogue and the exploration of differing perspectives.

Furthermore, conflicts can spark the search for creative and innovative solutions. As per Rahim (2023), when confronted with differing opinions or interests, individuals are motivated to think critically and explore alternative approaches. The need to find common ground or mutually beneficial outcomes encourages the generation of new ideas and strategies. Through collaborative problem-solving, conflicts can lead to the discovery of innovative solutions that might not have been considered in the absence of conflict.

In the field of psychology and conflict studies, conflicts can also be examined from two perspectives: interpersonal and intrapersonal (Khamidovna, 2021; Wilmot & Hocker (2017)). Interpersonal conflicts involve clashes between individuals or groups, while intrapersonal conflicts refer to internal struggles within an individual. Both perspectives contribute to a comprehensive understanding of conflicts, shedding light on the complexities of human interactions and the intricacies of individual experiences.

Interpersonal Conflict. Scholars such as Kurt Lewin, Morton Deutsch, and John W. Burton have made significant contributions to understanding the dynamics of conflicts that occur between individuals or groups. They explored the causes, processes, and resolution strategies related to interpersonal conflicts, highlighting the role of communication, power dynamics, and conflicting interests. In the words of Wilmot and Hocker (2017), interpersonal conflicts arise when individuals have differing goals and approaches, leading to potential personalization if not resolved promptly. These conflicts are a common occurrence in everyone's lives, including among friends, often

stemming from issues with communication. Further, according to Bao et al. (2016), Wilmot and Hocker defined interpersonal conflicts as the articulated clash between two or more interdependent parties who perceive opposing goals, limited resources, and mutual interference in goal attainment. This definition emphasizes the fundamental elements of conflicting goals, limited resources, and perceived interference.

The revival of face-to-face classes after the pandemic presents a complex landscape where interpersonal conflicts can arise among students, teachers, and other individuals within the educational context. As students return to physical classrooms, they may experience difficulties in readjusting to social dynamics, establishing new relationships, and adapting to changes in the learning environment. These challenges can give rise to conflicts as individuals navigate social norms, expectations, and personal boundaries. Moreover, differences in opinions, beliefs, and perspectives are likely to surface during in-person discussions, potentially leading to conflicts rooted in divergent viewpoints. These conflicts can disrupt the learning atmosphere and hinder effective communication and collaboration among students and teachers (Purwanto, 2020). In physical classrooms, the increased competition for recognition, resources, and academic achievements can create a highly charged environment where conflicts are more likely to occur. Students may feel the need to assert themselves and establish their positions within the social hierarchy of the classroom. This can lead to conflicts as they vie for attention, validation, and opportunities to shine academically (Tsiakara & Digelidis, 2021). The desire to outperform peers and gain recognition from teachers and classmates can create tensions and rivalries that contribute to conflicts.

Intrapersonal Conflict. The examination of conflicts from an intrapersonal perspective, which refers to conflicts within an individual's own mind or emotions, draws on the work of psychologists like Sigmund Freud, Carl Jung, and Fritz Perls. These theorists focused on intrapersonal conflicts arising from unconscious desires, inner tensions, and conflicting psychological needs. Generally, an intrapersonal conflict refers to a conflict that affects an individual internally, involving their own thoughts, feelings, opinions, values, and predispositions (Mack, 2018). This type of conflict arises when there is a struggle between what one "wants to do" and what one "should do" (Punia et al., 2021). In other words, it is a psychological conflict that occurs within an individual's mind, encompassing their thoughts, values, ideals, and emotions. Managing such conflicts can be challenging, leading to agitation, unease, and potentially even depression (Servidio et al., 2021).

In the context of transitioning back to face-to-face classes after the pandemic, intrapersonal conflicts can manifest as internal struggles, uncertainties, and anxieties that students may face (Wakui et al., 2021). These conflicts arise from the individual's thoughts, emotions, and beliefs, which can create challenges in adapting to the new learning environment. They may manifest in various subtypes, each highlighting specific internal struggles individuals may experience. When considering the transition back to face-to-face classes after the pandemic, these intrapersonal conflicts become particularly relevant.

Studies (see Nikmah et al., 2020; Nwachukwu et al., 2018; Zainal Badri & Wan Mohd Yunus, 2022) prove that the presence of intrapersonal conflicts related to one's role can potentially impact the well-being, stress levels, and academic performance of students. The development of effective time management skills, prioritization of responsibilities, and seeking support systems are crucial for students to successfully navigate conflicts. Academic institutions are tasked with the responsibility of providing resources, flexible scheduling options, and support services to aid students in effectively managing their roles and responsibilities.

Conflict Management Styles

Conflict management styles refer to the preferred approaches or strategies individuals adopt to handle conflicts and disagreements in various contexts (Ukata & Silas-Dikibo, 2020). These encompass a range of behaviors and techniques individuals employ to manage and resolve conflicts effectively, involving both assertive and cooperative actions (Espinoza et al., 2023). In the same vein, conflict management styles involve the methods individuals use to address and navigate conflicts, aiming to find mutually agreeable solutions and maintain positive relationships. These styles encompass distinct approaches, including tactics such as collaborating, competing,

avoiding, accommodating, and compromising, which individuals or groups may employ based on their preferences and the specific conflict situation (Rahim, 2023; Trueba et al., 2014).

Collaborating. Collaboration is a conflict management style that aims to find a mutually agreeable resolution to the problem (Espinoza et al., 2023). It involves actively pursuing win-win solutions, where the desires of all parties are taken into account without sacrificing one's own interests. Through collaboration, conflicts and disagreements that arise during the transition to face-to-face classrooms can be addressed in a constructive manner. Instead of resorting to confrontational or competitive approaches, collaborative efforts promote understanding, compromise, and consensus-building. It recognizes that returning to in-person learning is a shared endeavor that requires cooperation and collective problem-solving (Lee & Yang, 2023).

Competing. The competing conflict management method, as discussed by Rahim (2023), refers to a situation where individuals prioritize their own demands and objectives over those of others. It involves adopting a competitive stance, aiming to gain more power or influence through open hostility. This approach often involves the expression of anger, annoyance, or disagreement, and may even result in the removal of disputing parties through the use of authority. The competitive conflict management style involves a refusal to compromise and a determination to challenge the opinions and desires of others, as noted by McKibben (2017). It arises when one party firmly insists on a particular course of action and refuses to relent until their demands are met.

Avoiding. Avoiding, as a conflict management style, refers to an approach where individuals choose to ignore or evade conflict situations rather than address them directly. According to Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020), avoiding conflict occurs when individuals perceive the futility of discussing or confronting the issue and decide to disengage. Those who adopt the avoidance style often prioritize maintaining harmony and may intentionally avoid situations that could lead to potential conflicts.

Accommodating. Accommodating involves prioritizing the needs and desires of others over one's own (Espinoza et al., 2023). This approach is characterized by a recognition that maintaining positive relationships with others is more important than creating conflicts within the workplace. Individuals who adopt an accommodating approach have a strong desire for approval and acceptance from others, which means, individuals place the concerns of others ahead of their own (Ashraf et al., 2023). They willingly accommodate the needs and wants of others, often giving in or being persuaded to do so. In other words, with this style, individuals set aside their personal priorities and focus on the needs of others (Namwanje, 2023). Doing so allows minor conflicts to be resolved quickly and with minimal effort (Igwe & Okoye, 2023).

Compromising. Compromising, identified as a conflict management approach, entails pursuing a middle ground or reaching a solution that satisfies to some extent all parties involved (Zhang et al., 2015). It is a strategy where individuals are willing to make concessions and give up some of their own preferences in order to reach an agreement or resolve a conflict. The compromising style recognizes that not all conflicts can be fully resolved to everyone's satisfaction, and it aims to find a fair and acceptable outcome for all parties involved. According to Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020), compromising involves finding a solution that satisfies everyone to some extent. Rather than insisting on their own position or completely giving in to the other party, individuals using this approach are willing to meet in the middle. It is a strategy commonly used when the importance of finding a resolution outweighs the need for an ideal outcome, or when time constraints require a quick decision.

METHODS

Research design

The current study made use of a quantitative-descriptive research design. The design was considered appropriate for identifying the conflicts experienced by student nurses and describing the management styles they utilized in addressing these conflicts in a revived face-to-face learning modality. By utilizing a quantitative research

design, researchers can systematically and logically integrate various study components to effectively address the research problem (Chih-Pei & Chang, 2017; Mohajan, 2020). The use of a descriptive-quantitative research design in this study allowed for a detailed description and statistical analysis of the conflicts experienced and conflict management styles employed by student nurses during a specific period of revived face-to-face learning. The design aligns with the study's objectives, data collection method, timeframe, focus on description and analysis, and acknowledgment of limitations.

Research Locale and Respondents

The study occurred at a private Catholic university in the southern part of the Philippines. The university holds ISO certification and is accredited by the Philippine Accrediting Association of Schools, Colleges, and Universities (PAASCU). The study specifically focused on the Nursing Department of the College of Arts and Sciences.

The study utilized purposive sampling and made use of a set of selection criteria to determine eligible respondents; they must (1) be currently enrolled in the nursing program at the university, (2) have experience with online classes during the pandemic, and (3) be currently participating in the in-classroom (face-to-face) learning modality post-pandemic. The criteria made second-year and third-year BS Nursing students eligible to be respondents.

Fourth-year and first-year students were excluded from the study as they needed to meet the specified criteria. Fourth-year students had started their BS Nursing degree in an in-person setting, then shifted to online learning during the pandemic, and finally returned to in-person learning. On the other hand, first-year BS Nursing students had just begun their degree program in the current year, exclusively in an in-person setting.

The total number of respondents for this study was identified through Slovin's formula ($n=153$). Moreover, since two strata of students (i.e., second-year and third-year) were involved in the study, a stratified random sampling technique was then applied. Considering $n=153$, the respondents should have comprised 83 (54.25%) second-year and 70 (45.75%) third-year nursing students. However, only 144 respondents willingly agreed to participate in the study. Of the 144 respondents, 36 (25%) were second-year and 108 (75%) were third-year students.

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a two-part researcher-made survey questionnaire. The first part aimed to identify the type of conflicts commonly experienced by the respondents in a revived face-to-face learning modality. After a rigorous literature review and analysis, this part consisting of 20 items categorized into two types of conflicts: interpersonal (i.e., teacher-student, parent-student, and peer-student) and intrapersonal conflicts (i.e., motivational, moral, unfulfilled desire, role, adaptation, inadequate self-esteem, and neurotic).

The second part aimed to determine the respondents' management styles in addressing the conflicts they experienced in a revived face-to-face learning modality. This part was patterned from the study of Chandolia and Anastasiou (2020); necessary modifications were done to align the items with the current study's nature and objectives. The 10 items in this part could be categorized into five conflict management styles: collaborating, competing, avoiding, accommodating, and compromising.

For both parts, a five-point Likert scale was used in this part, adopted from the study of Nyutu et al. (2021), wherein 1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=neutral, 4=agree, and 5=strongly agree.

The content validity was established through a comprehensive literature review and analysis, which informed the development of the questionnaire items referring to conflicts in educational settings to identify relevant dimensions and constructs to be included in the questionnaire. Additionally, expert validation was employed, wherein

the instrument was reviewed by five experts in the field of education. These experts provided feedback and suggestions, which the researchers carefully considered in refining the instrument, ensuring its content validity.

Construct validity was ensured through the careful selection and categorization of questionnaire items based on theoretical frameworks and empirical evidence. The researchers structured the questionnaire into two distinct sections—one focusing on identifying types of conflicts and the other on assessing conflict management styles. The items were aligned with relevant theoretical frameworks, such as Rahim's model of conflict management styles, to ensure that the questionnaire accurately measured the underlying constructs of interest. Additionally, the researchers conducted a pilot test with a small sample of participants to assess the clarity and appropriateness of the questionnaire items.

Reliability testing was conducted to assess the consistency and stability of the instrument's measurements over time and across different samples. Internal consistency reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, which measures the degree of correlation between items within the questionnaire. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was found to be 0.76 for the underlying constructs of conflicts and 0.83 for conflict management styles, indicating acceptable internal consistency and supporting the validity and reliability of the instrument in accurately capturing respondents' experiences of conflicts and their approaches to managing them within a revived face-to-face learning modality.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

The researchers secured approval from concerned authorities to conduct the study. Following approved schedules, the researchers gathered the data by physically distributing the paper-and-pen survey questionnaires to the respondents in their respective classes. When the respondents answered, the researchers were present to provide any assistance and clarification needed by the respondents. Upon completion, the questionnaires were collected for quantitative analysis using specific statistical tools.

The data on the types of conflicts experienced by student nurses and the conflict management styles were analyzed through weighted mean and standard deviation (*SD*). In discussing the results, the three highest/lowest mean ratings and the overall mean and *SD* result were highlighted for the conflicts experienced; the two highest/lowest mean ratings and the overall mean and *SD* result were highlighted for the conflict management styles employed.

For the interpretation of mean scores, the range of means and their corresponding verbal descriptions and interpretations in Table 1 were considered:

Table 1
Range of Means and Interpretations

Range of Means	Verbal Description	Interpretation
4.21 – 5.00	Always	The respondents consistently or almost always experience the types of conflicts or exhibit the behaviors related to the question being asked.
3.41 – 4.20	Often	The respondents frequently experience the types of conflicts or exhibit the behaviors, but not as consistently as in the "Always" range.
2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	The respondents occasionally experience the types of conflicts or exhibit the behaviors, but not as frequently as in the "Often" range.

1.81 – 2.60	Rarely	The respondents rarely experience the types of conflicts or exhibit the behaviors, indicating that these aspects are not commonly encountered.
1.00 – 1.80	Never	The respondents never experience the types of conflicts or exhibit the behaviors in question, indicating that these aspects are entirely absent.

Potential Limitations

The researchers utilized a purposive sampling technique to select participants who met specific criteria, including being enrolled in the nursing program, having experience with online classes during the pandemic, and currently participating in face-to-face learning post-pandemic. While this sampling strategy may introduce biases by excluding certain student populations, such as fourth-year and first-year students, it was necessary to ensure that the participants had relevant experiences with both online and face-to-face learning modalities, aligning with the study's objectives. Additionally, to mitigate self-selection bias, efforts were made to maximize participation rates by physically distributing paper-and-pen survey questionnaires to the eligible respondents in their respective classes. Researchers were present to provide assistance and clarification as needed, fostering a supportive environment for respondents to complete the surveys. By actively engaging with the participants during data collection, the researchers aimed to minimize non-response bias and encourage a representative sample of student nurses to participate in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conflicts of Student Nurses in a Revived Face-to-face Classroom

Table 2 presents the results for this part. In terms of the conflict indicators which garnered the three highest mean ratings, findings reveal that Item 16 (I have experienced financial difficulties in my studies in a face-to-face setup), which is an intrapersonal conflict, particularly in the aspect of adaptation, got the highest weighted mean of 3.45 (*SD*= 1.13) and is interpreted as *often*.

The finding suggests that it is a prevalent personal issue among student nurses transitioning back to face-to-face learning after a period of distance education due to the pandemic, which could be rooted in the fact that the allocation of funds for board and lodging, transportation allowance, food, school supplies, and other miscellaneous expense is necessary to ensure that they can effectively engage in face-to-face learning and meet the requirements of the nursing program. However, these additional expenses may contribute to the overall financial burden student nurses and their families face, especially if they were already experiencing financial difficulties due to the pandemic or other factors (Abel, 2020; Barrot et al., 2021).

Table 2
Student Nurses' Conflicts in a Revived Face-to-face School Setup

Interpersonal Conflict					
Indicators	Conflict Subtype	Mean	SD	Interpretation	
1. I would like to raise my personal viewpoints with my instructors during face-to-face classes.	Teacher-student conflict	2.95	1.06	Always	
2. I would like to have clarifications with my teacher regarding the clarity of the lesson in the face-to-face classroom.		1.80	1.10	Never	
3. My parent's expectations make me feel like I have to do better in my performance at school than in online classes.	Parent-student conflict	3.08	1.31	Sometimes	
4. I felt timid due to lack of support of my parents in my onsite studies.		2.13	1.21	Rarely	
5. I felt that competition with my fellow students makes me feel tense during recitations in a revived face-to-face learning modality.	Peer-student conflict	2.48	1.20	Rarely	
6. I find it a challenge balancing studies and making new friends for this causes my academic concentration to diminish.		2.56	1.06	Rarely	
Intrapersonal Conflict					
7. I am not motivated due to a lack of praise and rewards that negatively affects my academic performance in a face-to-face class.	Motivational	2.33	1.11	Rarely	
8. I do not believe that my efforts will improve my performance academically during face-to-face classroom setup.		2.29	1.20	Rarely	
9. I experience dishonesty when it comes to checking paper tasks during a face-to-face setup.	Moral	2.48	1.06	Rarely	
10. I commit plagiarism in making work tasks such as journal readings in a face-to-face classroom.		1.99	1.11	Rarely	
11. After going back to school, I feel not sure anymore whether I am studying the right degree.	Unfulfilled Desire	2.77	1.20	Sometimes	
12. I am doubting myself if I'll be able to pass my school works in time during a face-to-face setup.		2.66	1.19	Sometimes	
13. I feel completely worthless as a member in doing group work activities in a classroom setting.	Role	2.40	1.15	Sometimes	
14. I am unable to perform my obligations as a student nurse in a face-to-face set up.		2.16	1.13	Sometimes	
15. My sleep is restless and I feel fatigued during RLE hours in a face-to-face setup.	Adaptation	3.17	1.18	Sometimes	

16. I have experienced financial difficulties in my studies in a face-to-face setup.		3.45	1.13	Often
17. I am anxious about how I perform academically in a face-to-face set up.	Inadequate Self-esteem	2.89	1.17	Sometimes
18. I am inclined to feel that I am a failure for the reason that my grades in an onsite class aren't as good as those in an online setup.		2.94	1.18	Sometimes
19. I am easily stressed out due to overthinking when it comes to studying for tests and exams in an onsite setting.	Neurotic	3.03	1.16	Sometimes
20. I am having a panic attack whenever I physically speak in front of my teacher and classmates because I feel that I am being criticized.		3.15	1.23	Sometimes
Overall Result		2.63	1.24	Sometimes

This implies that some student nurses find it hard to adapt to the new learning modality due to financial issues which create an internal conflict between their educational aspirations and the practical realities of limited financial resources, causing significant stress and emotional burden for them since the pressure of managing expenses and making ends meet can be overwhelming especially when they are adapting to the changes in the learning environment. These implications explain why returning to physical school after the pandemic can indeed pose financial challenges for students and their families, as the pandemic has had a significant impact on the economy, leading to widespread job losses, reduced income, and financial instability for many households (Szustak et al., 2021).

The second-highest weighted mean was obtained by Item 15 (My sleep is restless and I feel fatigued during RLE hours in a face-to-face setup), which is also an intrapersonal conflict in the same aspect of adaptation, with the mean of 3.17 ($SD= 1.18$) and is interpreted as *sometimes*.

The relatively high mean score indicates that this issue is somewhat prevalent among the respondents who might have become accustomed to online classes due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Their shift to face-to-face classes has involved a significant adjustment as they readapt to a different learning environment. This explains why this transition has disrupted their sleep patterns and resulted in restlessness and fatigue.

According to Muller and Mildenerger (2021), online classes generally provide students with more flexibility in terms of when they engage in learning activities. Students can often access pre-recorded lectures, assignments, and course materials at their convenience, allowing them to create their study schedules. This flexibility allows students to adapt their learning to their preferred times of productivity and can help them accommodate personal commitments and responsibilities (Garris & Fleck, 2022). This increased freedom could have contributed to differences in the experience of restlessness and fatigue between the two settings.

Lastly, Item 20 (I am having a panic attack whenever I physically speak in front of my teacher and classmates because I feel that I am being criticized) acquired the third-highest weighted mean of 3.15 ($SD=1.23$) and is interpreted as *sometimes*. This indicator falls again under the intrapersonal conflict category, but this time, in the neurotic aspect.

These findings indicate that while experiencing panic attacks may not be a constant experience for all students, it is still a significant concern for most respondents. As this conflict is neurotic, which refers to emotional instability, sensitivity, and a tendency to experience negative emotions such as anxiety or worry more intensely, it could be deduced that student nurses may feel anxious and uncomfortable when doing public speaking in the classroom context.

Literature suggests that online classes may create a deeper and wider sense of distance and less social pressure than face-to-face interactions (Unger & Meiran, 2020). Students may feel less observed and evaluated by their peers and teachers in this setting. The absence of physical presence and direct eye contact can alleviate the pressure to perform, decreasing anxiety (Yaniafari & Rihardini, 2021). Conversely, face-to-face classrooms often have a more evaluative atmosphere, with real-time feedback and immediate responses. In this context, students may worry about their performance, competence, or making mistakes, which can trigger anxiety and self-doubt (Spencer & Temple, 2021).

On the other hand, in terms of the conflict indicators which garnered the three lowest mean ratings, findings reveal that Item 2 (I would like to have clarifications with my teacher regarding the clarity of the lesson in the face-to-face classroom), which is an interpersonal conflict (i.e., teacher-student conflict), got the lowest weighted mean of 1.80 ($SD=1.10$) and is interpreted as *never*.

The finding implies that teachers might have successfully delivered clear and understandable lessons, minimizing the need for clarification or conflicts arising from unclear instructions. This suggests that returning to face-to-face classes may have improved communication channels between teachers and students; direct and immediate interaction in the physical classroom allows for real-time clarification and a better understanding of the lessons, reducing the likelihood of conflicts arising from misunderstandings.

In the study of Gopal et al. (2021), students, have generally claimed that face-to-face classes often provide an opportunity for them to receive immediate and personalized attention from teachers. This individualized support can contribute to a clearer understanding of the lessons, reducing the likelihood of conflicts or students needing further clarification. Moreover, it has been purported by other studies (see Bergiel et al., 2021; Dhawan, 2023; Rapanta et al., 2020) that the social dynamics of the physical classroom environment may foster positive relationships and effective communication between students and teachers.

The second-lowest weighted mean earner is Item 10 (I commit plagiarism in making work tasks such as journal readings in a face-to-face classroom) with a mean rating of 1.99 ($SD=1.11$) and is interpreted as *rarely*. This indicator belongs to the intrapersonal conflict category, particularly under the moral aspect.

The finding implies plagiarism could not prosper as a typical behavior among student nurses in a revived face-to-face classroom setup. This may suggest that student nurses value honesty and integrity in their academic pursuits. They recognize the importance of originality and ethical conduct in their work, reflecting a positive academic culture where students prioritize their learning and intellectual growth. Owunwanne et al. (2010) purport that an institution's effort is crucial in educating students about plagiarism and ethical behavior.

Nevertheless, when analyzed in the context of two different learning modalities (i.e., face-to-face vs online), it could be deduced that plagiarism can be limited in physical classrooms compared to online classrooms since in a physical classroom, instructors have the opportunity to observe students during assessments and assignments directly. This direct supervision is a deterrent to plagiarism, as students know that their actions are being monitored (Glendinning, 2014). The presence of instructors and peers creates a sense of accountability and reduces the temptation to engage in dishonest practices (Abbasi et al., 2021).

Furthermore, students typically have limited access to external resources in a physical classroom setting, especially during assessments. This restriction reduces the opportunities for students to copy or plagiarize from external sources. In contrast, online classrooms may provide students unrestricted access to digital resources, making it easier to copy and paste information without proper attribution (Khan et al., 2021; Mansoor et al., 2022).

Finally, Item 4 (I felt timid due to the lack of support from my parents in my onsite studies), which is an interpersonal conflict (i.e., parent-student), received the third-lowest weighted mean of 2.13 ($SD=1.21$) and is interpreted as *rarely*.

The relatively low mean rating and the interpretation of "rarely" indicate that the respondents do not commonly report this experience of feeling timid due to a lack of parental support. While Item 16 (I have experienced financial difficulties in my studies in a face-to-face setup) got the highest weighted mean in this study which suggests that financial matter is a prevalent personal issue among student nurses and their families, this finding underscores that they embrace the importance of fostering effective communication and support within the parent-student relationship. They could have understood that open lines of communication, mutual understanding, and shared goals can help alleviate timidity and create a supportive academic environment for students to thrive.

Such an interpretation corroborates the findings from the study of Gayatri and Irawaty (2022), which states that effective communication in the face of financial struggles can enable family members to work together as a team, brainstorm solutions, and make collective decisions. It fosters empathy, understanding, and emotional support, which are essential for navigating challenging times. Additionally, building a strong connection among family members in the face of life adversities can help prevent misunderstandings, conflicts, and isolation within the family unit (Braithwaite, 2001; Galvin et al., 2015).

Generally, the findings on the conflicts experienced by student nurses in a revived face-to-face learning modality got an overall weighted mean of 2.63 ($SD=1.24$) as is interpreted as *sometimes*. It suggests that conflicts are not constant or pervasive but occur periodically or intermittently during the transition process. This finding highlights the periodical challenges and conflicts that student nurses may encounter as they navigate the shift from online learning to in-person instruction.

Published studies state that transitioning back to face-to-face classes after a period of remote learning presents numerous challenges for students (Detyna et al., 2023; Ryan et al., 2023; Singer et al., 2023). It is because adapting to a new learning environment, reestablishing social connections, adjusting to academic expectations, managing logistical considerations, and addressing health and safety concerns all contribute to the complexity of this transition. Hence, to facilitate a smoother transition, educational institutions should establish a range of support services to assist students during transitional periods. This may include academic counseling, mentoring programs, tutoring services, and career guidance. By offering these resources, institutions can provide students with the necessary tools and guidance to navigate challenges and succeed academically as research has indicated that students who actively utilize these support services are more likely to experience higher levels of academic success and personal growth (Grissom & Condon, 2021; Kim et al., 2021).

Conflict Management Styles of Student Nurses in a Revived Face-to-face Classroom

Table 3

Student Nurses' Conflict Management Styles in a Revived Face-to-face School Setup

Indicators	Type	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. I am seeking help from my fellow student nurses in working out a group project in a face-to-face setting.	Collaborating	3.28	0.98	Sometimes
2. I physically share my problem with my classmates so that they can help me address it.		2.60	1.07	Rarely
3. I try to show to my classmates the logic and the benefits that I have in a classroom setting.	Competing	2.89	1.05	Sometimes
4. During class recitations, I do my best more than others to meet the		2.82	0.90	Sometimes

expectations of my clinical instructors.				
5. I try not to take any positions or responsibilities in order to prevent confrontation with my group members.	Avoiding	3.04	1.09	Sometimes
6. I attempt to delay talking to my fellow student nurses about a rising problem in school until I've had time to think about it.		2.80	1.02	Sometimes
7. I'd rather accept my groupmate's answer than my own in a group quiz in school.	Accommodating	3.09	1.10	Sometimes
8. If it makes one of my fellow student nurses happy, I might let them keep their opinion in a face-to-face group work.		3.17	1.02	Sometimes
9. I am willing to give up several opinions in order to acquire other opinions during discussion in a face-to-face set up.	Compromising	3.10	0.93	Sometimes
10. I am willing to set aside my feelings for others rather than confront them to their wrong doings towards the face-to-face policy of the nursing department.		3.25	1.03	Sometimes
Overall Result		3.00	1.04	Sometimes

Table 3 presents the results for this part. In terms of the conflict management style indicators which garnered the two highest mean ratings, findings reveal that Item 1 (I am seeking help from my fellow student nurses in working out a group project in a face-to-face setting), which pertains to a collaborating conflict management style, obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.28 ($SD=0.98$) and interpreted as *sometimes*.

The finding implies that student nurses occasionally seek help and work with fellow student nurses to resolve conflicts or issues related to their group project in a face-to-face environment. This could be fortified by the assertion that face-to-face interactions allow for richer and more nuanced communication than in online classrooms.

This interpretation aligns with the findings of various studies (Chen & Chen, 2022; Heilporn & Lakhal, 2021), which assert that face-to-face classrooms facilitate spontaneous interactions and discussions. In such settings, student nurses have the opportunity to engage in impromptu conversations, exchange ideas, and brainstorm solutions. These spontaneous interactions not only foster creativity but also encourage active participation and a sense of shared ownership over projects. Furthermore, the social connections and rapport forged through face-to-face interactions contribute to the creation of a supportive environment where student nurses feel more comfortable seeking help, collaborating with peers, and collectively resolving conflicts (Brocato et al., 2015; Kaufmann & Vallade, 2022; Zheng et al., 2022). The emphasis on face-to-face interactions underscores the importance of physical classrooms in facilitating meaningful learning experiences and interpersonal connections among student nurses.

The second-highest mean rating earner is Item 10 (I am willing to set aside my feelings for others rather than confront them about their wrongdoings towards the face-to-face policy of the nursing department), which is a compromising style, got the mean rating of 3.25 ($SD=1.03$) and is interpreted as *sometimes*.

The respondents seem willing to compromise and avoid face-to-face confrontations, possibly to maintain harmony or avoid conflict among themselves. They may have thought that as professional nurses in the future, they are expected to be contributors to a cooperative and non-confrontational work environment, fostering teamwork and reducing tension among colleagues.

According to Aydin and Dinc (2017), Nesje (2017), and Santos et al. (2016), nurses are expected to play a vital role in creating a positive and harmonious work environment. This is crucial for achieving optimal patient care, enhancing the well-being of staff members, facilitating effective problem-solving, reducing stress and burnout, promoting professional growth, and cultivating a positive organizational culture.

In terms of the conflict management style indicators which garnered the two lowest mean ratings, findings reveal that Item 2 (I physically share my problem with my classmates so that they can help me address it), a collaborating conflict management style, received the lowest mean rating of 2.6 ($SD=1.07$) as is interpreted as *rarely*.

It can be understood that student nurses do not frequently engage in the collaborating conflict management style when it comes to sharing their problems with classmates. Student nurses may be less likely to actively seek their classmates' assistance in addressing their problems. They may prefer to handle their problems individually or rely on other sources of support instead of collaborating with their peers. This further suggests a potential gap in the collaborative approach to conflict management among student nurses, as it may appear contradictory to the result showing the highest mean rating in this study which indicates nursing students' preference for the collaborating conflict management style; however, it is essential to highlight that student nurses' willingness to collaborate appears to be primarily focused on academic matters, as indicated by Item 1 (I am seeking help from my fellow student nurses in working out a group project in a face-to-face setting).

Nurses play a crucial role in healthcare by not only providing essential medical assistance but also fostering a nurturing environment that promotes patients' overall well-being (Barnes, 2015). However, navigating the delicate balance between professional obligations and personal interactions is paramount to uphold the integrity of nursing practice. When confronted with personal matters from patients, such as emotional distress or non-medical concerns, nurses must exercise caution to prevent the blurring of professional boundaries (Ward-Griffin et al., 2015). Maintaining clear boundaries ensures that nurses can deliver care objectively and effectively, without compromising the quality of their services. In situations where patients require support beyond the scope of nursing practice, it is incumbent upon nurses to refer them to appropriate resources, such as social workers, counselors, or specialized professionals, who can address their specific needs with expertise and sensitivity (Briones-Vozmediano et al., 2022). By adhering to these principles, nurses uphold professional standards while ensuring that patients receive comprehensive care and support tailored to their individual circumstances.

The second-lowest mean rating earner is Item 6 (I attempt to delay talking to my fellow student nurses about a rising problem in school until I've had time to think about it), an avoiding conflict management style. It has a mean score of 2.8 ($SD=1.02$), interpreted as *sometimes*.

Despite it being the lowest mean rating earner, it could still be interpreted that as future nurses, like other individuals and professionals, they may at times choose to employ an avoiding conflict management style just to preserve healthy connections with heads and peers.

Conflict within healthcare settings can involve complex power dynamics (Morley & Cashell, 2017). In that contest, nurses may sometimes avoid conflict when dealing with superiors, such as doctors or administrators, to mitigate potential professional consequences or maintain positive working relationships. They may perceive that confronting the issue directly could lead to undesirable outcomes or impact their career prospects (Aberese-Ako et al., 2015; Moreland & Apker, 2016; Pitsillidou et al., 2018).

Overall, the findings on the conflict management styles employed by student nurses in a revived face-to-face learning modality got an overall weighted mean of 3.00 ($SD=1.04$) as is interpreted as *sometimes*. This suggests that student nurses may employ various approaches to manage conflicts that arise within the classroom setting. Within the face-to-face learning context, respondents may perceive opportunities for professional growth, recognizing the value of developing conflict management skills essential for their future roles as nurses. The physical presence of clinical instructors and fellow students facilitates immediate feedback and in-depth discussions, fostering the acquisition of effective conflict resolution abilities. As Labrague et al. (2017) elucidated, integrating practical conflict resolution training into nursing education equips students with the necessary skills for their future careers. By incorporating conflict resolution education into the curriculum, educational institutions empower students to navigate interpersonal conflicts confidently and professionally, ultimately enhancing their readiness to advocate for patients' well-being with empathy and competence (Marañón & Pera, 2015). This emphasis on conflict resolution skills not only benefits students' personal and professional development but also contributes to the overall quality of healthcare delivery.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study concludes that student nurses dominantly experienced intrapersonal conflicts in transitioning from online to face-to-face learning. Financial difficulties emerged as a significant conflict causing stress due to limited financial resources, which affected their ability to meet program requirements. The shift in learning modalities also disrupted sleep patterns, leading to restlessness and fatigue during practical training hours. Moreover, many student nurses reported experiencing anxiety and discomfort when speaking to their peers and teachers.

Moreover, considering the findings about their conflict management styles, the study concludes that student nurses often employed collaborating and compromising approaches. They occasionally collaborated and sought help from their fellow student nurses to address conflicts arising from group projects, benefitting from the opportunities for rich communication and real-time interactions in face-to-face settings. Additionally, they demonstrated a willingness to compromise and maintain harmony by setting aside personal feelings to avoid confrontation.

Furthermore, it could be concluded that student nurses were less likely to actively seek their classmates' help in addressing their personal problems, indicating a preference for individual problem-solving or seeking support from other sources. Likewise, while some respondents chose to delay discussions about rising problems until they had time to think, it was not a predominant behavior among the respondents, suggesting limited use of the avoiding conflict management style.

In general, they tended to employ different conflict management approaches, primarily collaborating and compromising, to resolve conflicts in the classroom. This indicates their willingness to actively engage with peers and maintain a cooperative work environment, which aligns with the skills needed for their future nursing careers.

The study's conclusions are contingent upon certain limitations, such as the reliance on self-reported data, which may introduce response biases and limit the depth of understanding regarding conflicts and their management among student nurses. Additionally, the study focused solely on a single university and may not fully capture the diversity of experiences across different educational institutions or regions. Future research could explore alternative methodologies, such as mixed-methods approaches, to delve deeper into the intricacies of financial difficulties, conflicts, and conflict management styles in nursing education. Furthermore, a correlational study could examine the relationships between demographics, conflict types, and conflict management styles employed by student nurses, offering valuable insights into potential influencing factors.

Additionally, based on the study's results, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Student nurses should seek part-time employment opportunities within the healthcare sector to gain practical experience and financial support. Stakeholders could collaborate with local healthcare facilities to establish internship or shadowing programs tailored to student nurses' schedules.

- ii. The university may implement a sleep wellness program, managed by the student government and student affairs office, to improve students' overall health and well-being, including student nurses.
- iii. They may also designate a "Mental Health Awareness Month" with workshops and events focusing on stress management and seeking help for mental health concerns.
- iv. They may as well organize "Transition Chit-Chat Sessions" to foster support and camaraderie among student nurses during their transition. These sessions could be structured as informal gatherings facilitated by faculty members, peer mentors, or student support services staff. The goal is to provide a space where student nurses can come together to share their experiences, express concerns, and offer mutual support. Activities within these sessions may include group discussions, peer-led workshops on coping strategies, and collaborative problem-solving exercises.

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